

AI-PRISM Reveals its Final Results

Welcome to the final AI-PRISM Newsletter!

In this edition of the AI-PRISM Newsletter, we reflect on the Project Final Meeting held in Valencia and share highlights from the project demonstrations, along with a selection of recent events and key achievements from across the consortium.

As the year draws to a close, we would also like to extend our best wishes for a relaxing holiday break and all the best for the year ahead.

AI-PRISM Journey

AI-PRISM Final Meeting in Valencia – Reflecting on Three Years of Collaboration

#AIPRISMevents

FINAL PROJECT MEETING | Valencia, Spain | 3-4 December 2025

The AI-PRISM consortium gathered in Valencia on 3-4 December 2025 for its final project meeting, hosted by the Universitat Politècnica de València. The event offered an

opportunity to review the full scope of results achieved over the past three years, ranging from technological innovation to human-centred design, standardisation work and exploitation planning.

[Find out more](#)

Watch Our Recap!

Demonstrations

[Watch our Demonstrations Playlist!](#)

The AI-PRISM Final Project Meeting continues with a strong focus on the demonstration sites and use cases now ending their final stage of development. The project's solutions are being validated across five industrial domains:

- Furniture – Chair Design
- Electronics – Semiconductor Processes
- Food & Beverages
- Home Appliances – Consumer Goods
- Discrete Manufacturing

These pilots show how AI-PRISM integrates AI, robotics and human-centred design to support safer, more efficient and more flexible production environments.

You can discover the full demonstrations, scenarios and technical explanations on our website and YouTube channel "Demonstartions playlist".

[Watch videos](#)

AI-PRISM Open-Access Alliance

[Join the Open-Access Alliance!](#)

AI-PRISM OPEN·ACCESS ALLIANCE

THE EUROPEAN
DIGITAL INNOVATION HUB
IN TRANSILVANIA

The **AI-PRISM Open-Access Alliance** builds on the technical solutions and pilot cases from the AI-PRISM project to broaden access to its results. It aims to create a stakeholder ecosystem that supports the reuse of these outcomes in various scenarios, fosters the development of new human-centric, AI-powered smart manufacturing solutions, and drives new business opportunities.

AI-PRISM has just launched a short questionnaire to gather interest from potential stakeholders who would like to join the AI-PRISM Open Access Alliance. If you're interested in becoming a member, we encourage you to **complete the form!**

Watch the Open-Access Alliance Platform Launch!

AI-PRISM Alliance Management Structure

The diagram shows a hierarchical structure: Management committee at the top, followed by Coordinator, Technical coordinator, and Secretary. Below these are the Technical committee and Delivery and supervision committee. To the right is a pyramid diagram with layers: Inter-org, Inter-org, Evaluation, Roles, Rights, Duties, Control, Rules, Behaviour, and Principles (Honesty, Commitment, Mutual respect). A vertical bar on the right side of the pyramid is labeled 'Multi-stakeholder'.

Bogdan Mursa

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[Fill in the Questionnaire](#)

AI-PRISM Events

AI-PRISM at the European Big Data Value Forum 2025 – Reflections on a Strategic Presence

Our recent participation at EBDVF 2025 offered a timely opportunity to observe how the broader data and AI community is evolving, and to reflect on where the AI-PRISM initiative currently stands. Hosted between 12–14 November in Copenhagen, this year's forum gathered more than 470 participants, 53 partners and sponsors, 43 sessions, and 24 exhibition booths — numbers that illustrate both the scale and the diversity of Europe's AI and data ecosystem.

[Read more](#)

AI-PRISM at AI Expo Korea 2025

At this year's **AI Expo Korea**, the Electronics and Telecommunications Research Institute (**ETRI**) presented developments from the **AI-PRISM project**. Co-exhibiting with leading technology providers AMD, AAEON, Renesas, and NXP at the Avnet booth, ETRI demonstrated how AI-powered systems can elevate efficiency, safety, and adaptability in small-scale and manual industrial settings. AI EXPO Korea featured 544 exhibition booths and 322 companies from 18 countries. More than 43,000 people attended the event.

[Read more](#)

2nd prize in the Neura Robotics Challenge at KI Palooza 2025

Congratulations to our partner team from KU Leuven – Santiago Iregui, Federico Ulloa Rios, Jasper Van der Auwera, and Johan Ubbink – for winning 2nd prize in the Neura

Their innovative mobile manipulator for industrial cable harness applications impressed the jury and highlighted the impact of human-centric AI and robotics in smart manufacturing.

AI-PRISM Highlighted at IDENTICOM4 2025

The AI-PRISM project was featured at IDENTICOM4 – Industry and Technology Fair, held at Cluj Innovation Park between May 20–22, 2025, with representation from Transilvania IT Cluster and The European Digital Innovation Hub in Transilvania (TEDIHT). The event brought together key regional and national stakeholders to explore the future of smart manufacturing, industrial automation and digital transformation.

[Learn more](#)

AI and Human-Robot Collaboration for Sustainable Microrobotic Assembly in Semiconductor Manufacturing

At the CoDIT 2025 conference Tomasz Kołcon from Łukasiewicz-PIAP Institute, and Krystian Goławski from VIGO Photonics presented the research and results from Polish pilot site of AI-PRISM project.

[Learn more](#)

STAY TUNED TO THE AI-PRISM SMART JOURNEY

AI-PRISM Horizon Europe

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